

Values' Education Model for Islamic Education Institutions in Indonesia: A Study of Al-Basyariyah Modern Islamic School

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 10, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: May 14, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords</p> <p>Integrative model, Value education, Modern Pesantren, Interpretative-Hermeneutics, Religious-Pedagogics</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3827732</p>	<p><i>This study is conducted in the context of developing values education through in-depth study on the educational phenomenon in Islamic education institutions in Indonesia. The study aims to formulate an integrative values education model for schools, especially Islamic schools (madrasah) in the context of character building. To attain the target, empirical data is collected through a case study at Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School in Bandung. The techniques used for data collection are participatory observation, interview and document analysis. Data analysis is by interpretative-hermeneutics approach. Findings show that the model of education in Al-Basyariyah Islamic boarding institution combines two modes of Islamic education systems, the Islamic boarding school (Pesantren) system and the Madrasah Tsanawiyah/Aliyah system integrated as one. Islamic boarding schools strives to build students' characters through Islam by applying a strict code of discipline and conduct. Education activities are based on spiritual values that emanate from God's goodness, love, and benevolence, and on the responsibility of human beings. In conclusion, an Integrative Values Education Model in Modern Islamic Boarding School can be formulated as a systemic pattern of the education process integrating all education components and sub-components (goals, human-dimensions, subject-matter, methods, educational facilities, agents of education, environment and evaluation system) harmoniously, and eliminating conflict, based on religious norms and consciousness, in process nurturing students towards Islamic self-actualization based on both religious knowledge and secular knowledge.</i></p>

Introduction

This study is triggered by the discrepancy between the national education objectives in Indonesia that are laden with values education and the realization that education as a whole has not met the expectations of developing a national character. The discrepancy occurs because: (a) values education is only a small part of the curriculum structure; (b) values education only relies on the classroom teaching approach; (c) the development of the values education models adopt a secular-Western approach that is based more on the aspects of spirituality and desire; and (d) values education is separated from the strengthening factors like faith. This calls for a solution in form of alternative values education model development that can render values education more effective in developing character and personality. However, values education model development is a very crucial aspect because model development entails a latent humanistic aspect. Values education also entails two complex matters of education and values. In the context of developing character and personality, educational efforts are more complex because personality does not exist in a passive individual; instead, it exists in an individual who has will and commitment to take his or her own decision.

Assumptively, the researcher argues that in order to arrive at a solution, there should be development of an integrative model in values education, a model in which all segments in the process of personality establishment is given attention in the efforts of value development. The development is based on the consideration that personality is an inseparable unit that cannot be divided (Jumsai, 2008:7). Meanwhile, education refers to integral activities (Pranarka, 1987:30).

In order to have a strong empirical foundation, educational model development should start from human experience acquired to successfully accomplish an educational mission in the context of character development. In relation to this statement, a question can be raised here: What are the appropriate ways of developing a values education model that is derived from field experience?

The methodological educational model, in terms of the Habermasian philosophical approach, more specifically in terms of values education, is developed for the sake of the practical importance. Therefore, in order to be the basis of scientific development, the development of values education methodology should pay attention to the following matters: (a) the study for the values education development should be grounded; (b) educational phenomena, as a complex humanistic phenomena, demand reflective interpretation in order to understand its meaning; (c) the meaning of the successfully captured phenomena should have orientation towards the formulation of the values education model that can be applied in a practical setting of the values education process.

Based on the ontological and the epistemological background highlighted above, the researcher conducted a study on ontological and epistemological basis with the following principles: (a) empirical study on an institution that is historically considered as relatively successful in developing character and personality through the values inculcation. In this case an Islamic boarding school; (b) conduct a scientific concept and approach that is in accordance with the characters of the object under review i.e. the Habermasian scientific philosophy; and (c) use the empirical facts as raw material for further reflection to develop a model that can be applied in a practical setting.

Based on the principles, a study is conducted on Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding where the researcher observed, analyzed and interpreted the educational phenomena with the interpretative-hermeneutical approach. Therefore, the main problem of study is: What is the effect of the integrative values education model developed through the interpretative-hermeneutical study on the phenomenon of values education in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School?

Literature Review

Education in developing Character

Although Ewing & Moore in Kattsoff (1986:334) state that values are an empirical quality that cannot be defined, values are considered as a product of human creation and imagination (Ibrahim, 1978:26), values are matter that exists in reality; the real life that human beings experience. Values emanate from individual awareness when one responds to the "world" one is aware of. Knikker (1977:4) notes that values are an integral part of the humanistic experience.

From the various definitions by Fraenkel (1977:6), Dewey in Darmodihardjo (1986:36), Encyclopaedia Britannica (1963:963), Djahiri (1989:4), Knikker (1977:3) and Winecoff (1987:31) that relate values to the attitudes, values can be defined as follows:

- Human ideas in the form of thinkable or appreciative concepts and of a group of attitudes
- Provided by individuals or group of individuals
- Related to the quality of the objects that is realized
- Considered to be important and useful for the life
- Encouraged and also serving as guidance in deciding actions

In empirical-cultural manner, values are related to the concept of truth, kindness, beauty and holiness; the meaning of right-wrong, good-bad, beautiful-ugly and sacred-profane towards objects. There are specific-individual subjective values and general-universal objective values (Kohlberg in Djahiri, 1996:26).

Values, by individuals, are turned into standards for considering which actions are decent and indecent, good and not good, useful and useless and for deciding which actions are liked and disliked. In the more complex matters, values help an individual to decide whether a matter, object, individual, idea lifestyle and alike – is

good or bad (Fraenkel, 1977:7). The most important standard for an individual is the moral or ethical values because moral values represent guides to what is right and just (Fraenkel, 1977:7).

Ethics, in terms of basic concept, can be classified into multiple orientations. First, the ethics can be classified into the teleological ethics that have oriented towards objectives of Aristotelian Eudaimonism and the Epicurean Hedonism, or the Urban Idealism, as well as the Bentham or Mill Utilitarianism (Kattsoff, 1986:359-368). Second, the ethics can be classified into the deontological ethics that emphasize conscience decisions such as the Kantian moral (Asdi, 1997:120-123). Third, ethics be classified into the theological ethics that emphasize that kindness comes from God (Kattsoff, 1986:371-374).

Then, the epistemological ethics appear in multiple schools of ethics philosophy such as Absolute Rationalism, Absolute Idealism, Utilitarianism, Structuralism and Relativism. Absolute Rationalism developed by Kant (Asdi, 1977:116) ensures that morality exists because of imperative-categorical aspects that an individual commit something due to the awareness toward the responsibility. The imperative-categorical aspect is an order or an imperative that does not entail certain requirements (Ibrahim, 1980:185; Asdi, 1997:120). On the other hand, Absolute Idealism introduced by Hegel is based on the spirit of metaphysics that transforms to exist 'in-and-for-himself' (An und fur Sich). In his opinion, reality is a spirit that in development, is differentiated into three categories: subjective-spirit, objective-spirit and absolute-spirit (Peursen, 1991:173). The ethics and morality are in the setting of objective-spirit discussion in which the rational will is turned into the objects of the general life (Hadiwiyono, 1980:103).

Utilitarianism developed by Jeremy Bentham (1748-1832) notes that the moral fit of an action is decided merely by its usefulness in providing the basis of happiness or enjoyment. Bentham in Bertens, (1993:246-148) established the premises as his conceptual foundation in which, in his opinion, moral theory should be concrete, not abstract and measurable. Structuralism as developed by Jean Piaget (1896-1980), states that community, culture and individual spirit contains structures that can be understood objectively. In his opinion, organisms organize their experience by creating mental structures and apply the mental structures into these experiences (Kneller, 1984:101). Meanwhile, Kohlberg applies the Structuralism approach into the development of moral theory. In his opinion, moral consideration is a result of cognitive structure, which is the result of organisms' interaction with their social environment. These stages can be classified into six phases (Kneller, 1984:11). Meanwhile, Moral Relativism views that ethics and morality are relative, depending on the condition and the context that surrounds the moral relativism in all the social, the cultural, the spatial, the temporal or the trust and the belief aspects.

Values Education as a Process of Being Homo Ethicus

The importance of education for the individual is the convention of human beings along history. Experts agree that human beings are unfinished organisms at the time they are borne. In order to enable their life as human beings and to conduct their life tasks as human beings, these organisms should be raised and be educated by human beings in their environment (Soelaeman, 1988:43). Without being raised and educated, human potential is stunted and undirected, therefore education is a human need. The human beings are homo educandum et educabile, organisms that can be educated (Said, 1989:19). The education itself is defined variedly; from multiple definitions provided by Butler (Liang-Gie, 1998:12), George Counts and John Child (Morris, 1966:106), Soelaeman (1988:45) and some of the Existentialists disciples (Morris, 1966:110,135), the researcher has found that in education there are the following aspects:

- Human development
- Actualization of disposition (fitrah), namely the potential power provided since the birth in form of spirit, reason, feeling, intention and creation
- Provision by the influencing people
- The objective of humanizing a human as an independent and responsible personality
- The socio-cultural context

In the context of values education, values can be defined in its position both as a *genetivus-objectivus* and as a *genetivus-subjectivus*. As a *genetivus-objectivus*, the values education has the connotation of inculcating values or of values-inculcation. On the other hand, as a *genetivus-subjectivus* the values education has the connotation of clarifying values or of values-clarification.

According to Djahiri (1996:67), values education has the following roles: (1) to grow the values awareness; (2) to straighten values orientation; (3) to develop independence in deciding values; (4) to inculcate humanistic values; (5) to sharpen values appreciation; and (6) to provide capabilities in solving values conflict. In this definition, there are two directions of the values education namely values incultation and values clarification.

However, the modern definition of values education refers to a process of assisting students in testing existing values through critical analysis to improve their reasoning and in developing their own set of values (Wincoff, 1987:3,4). According to Downey & Kelly (1982) through moral education people expect that morally educated men is generated, referring to the individuals who: (1) have relevant factual knowledge in relation to each issues in which moral decisions should be made; (2) have social skills to interact and to cooperate with other people; and (3) have understanding of the feelings of other people which is also known as moral behavior. This mater involves the affective and the emotional dimension.

From the above explanation, it can be concluded that values education in the modern definition (read: The Western definition) is to assist students in clarifying and in confirming their self-values in the efforts of pursuing their moral maturity in adopting and internalizing their internal values. These efforts are conducted through rational reasoning, cognitive development, affective development and habituation in their actions strengthen their commitment towards values based on their own self-awareness. According to Kant, intellectual education is important. However, all knowledge is useless and even dangerous if not backed-up with moral character. Even the core of the educational objective is to develop ethical awareness. The aim of education is first to develop a human being with a sense of dignity and duty (Brumbaugh & Lawrence, 1963:101-102). Coomb (Djahiri, 1996:2) also confirms this with the statement: Value education or none at all.

Orientation Variety in the Value Education Models

There are multiple models in values education that are developed in Western countries with multiple methodological orientations. However, in general these approaches are focused more on the rational weighing capacity development in taking moral decisions. As a result, morality is reduced rational excuses that can be turned into the basis in deciding actions considered good. From the results of analysis of multiple values education models developed nowadays, the following orientations are found: cognitivist, effectuality, habituality and spiritualist. From the four orientations, there are more variants, which are a synthesis of these orientations, these include:

Cognitivist

The cognitivist approach is first developed by Immanuel Kant who considered that the moral awareness exists in the internal part of humans (Magnis-Suseno, 2003:137-154). However, the moral action is a result of consideration from the reasoning activity known as practical logic (*der praktischen vernunft*). There are several approaches that belong to the Cognitivism namely the Value Clarification Technique developed by Raths, Harmin & Simon (Hersh et al., 1980:75; Wincoff, 1987:7.1) and the Value Analysis Model developed by Jerrold Coomb, Milton Mieux & James Chadwick (Hersh et al., 1980:99). In addition, the Rational Building Model developed by James Shaver and the Cognitive Moral Development Model that developed by Lawrence Kohlberg (Hersh et al., 1980:119; Wincoff, 1981:1).

Affectualist

The approach that belongs to the affectualist orientation is the Consideration Model that developed first by Peter McPhail. The model is also based on the belief that the human fundamental need is to live equally with the other people, to love and to be loved (Winecoff, 1987:6.1,6.2). Figures like May, Krathwoll and Phillip Coomb can also be put in the affectualist category.

Habituality

Habituality orientation views that values awareness and morality is a result of habituation due to interaction with the environment. Values education is an internalization training by means of habituations. Aristoteles emphasized that communal living has to be moralized or ethical people (Magnis-Suseno, 2003:32-35). Approaches that belong to this orientation include Dewey Progressivism (Howard, 1992:34-50) and the Social Learning Model (Djahiri, 1996:54).

Spiritualist

People of the spiritualist orientation believe that true values are God-given values. Human beings only have one option, that is to be fully associated to values, whether they like it or not, under the basis of faith. The commitment towards value is based on the sacred awareness that impacts deeds and sins. Approaches that belong to the spiritualist orientation are the Thomist, Gazalian, Perennialist and Religion Absolutism.

Cognitive-Affectualist

The Cognitive-Affectualist people view that ethics consideration does not only involve reason but also emotion. Figures of this orientation Downey & Kelly (1982:30), combine Kant Rationalism and the Kohlberg Structuralism.

Eclecticism

Values consideration involves all aspects of human life namely: knowledge (the cognitive aspect), emotion (the affective aspect), habit (the habitual aspect) and internal awareness (the spiritual aspect). The proponent of this orientation is Lickona (Djahiri, 1996:55). In addition, the importance of inculcating values, especially values derived from religion, culture, science or from political and institutional settings belong to this orientation as well (Djahiri, 1996:60-62).

Third Level Headings

Please use 12-point bold for first-level headings, 10-point bold for second-level headings, and 10-point italics for third -level headings with an initial capital letter for any proper nouns. Leave one blank line after each heading and two blank lines before each heading. (Exception: leave one line between consecutive headings.) Please margin all headings to the left.

Method

The target of this study is to design an integrative values education model that can be implemented in values education practice for character development in the schools. In order to achieve the target, empirical data is collected through a case study on Al-Basyriyah Islamic Boarding School by qualitative approach. The method applied in this study is the qualitative-interpretative approach and in order to attain the necessary data and information, the researcher applied the grounded-research model. The approach bases all analysis on the data and the facts found naturally in the field. The techniques applied in this study are as follows: (1) Observation and Participatory Observation; (2) Documentation and Library Study of books and the texts regarding to Islamic Boarding Schools, the educational textbooks, the letters and the other notes published by and on

Islamic Boarding Schools; and (3) Interviews on Islamic Boarding School members, supervisors, teachers and students or the santri.

Data interpretation is by applying the interpretative-hermeneutic approach. The interpretative-hermeneutic approach is a research method that intended for the humaniora science in the Habermasian Science Philosophy. The implementation of interpretative-hermeneutic approach toward the data in the study is conducted by combining the basic concepts and principles proposed by the hermeneutics developers, in text form and human phenomena, like Scheleiermacher, Heidegger, Dilthey and Ricouer. These basic principles are adapted to the characteristics of the educational phenomena and the researcher's interests in order to achieve the objective of the study, which is integrative values education model in the tradition of Islamic Boarding Schools. In this case, the four hermeneutic aspects are given attention (normative, technical, social and historical), the hermeneutic circles, the phenomenological deconstruction and the interests.

In order to eliminate ambiguity and the misperceptions, several terms should be explained in relation to meanings intended by the researcher. These include:

Integrative Values Education Model

The teaching model by Robert J. Schaeffer (Bruce Joyce & Marscha Weil, 1972:xii) is structured logically, consistent, cohesive, and lucidly describes alternative patterns of teaching. The Values education model, intended in this study is a systematic pattern in the process of educating values to learners in order to achieve an educational objective that can be replicated by other educational institutions in order to achieve the same educational objective. Then, the integrative values education model in this study refers to a systemic pattern in which multiple components and sub-components are involved in the educational process in an intermingle and concomitant manner as a single unit so that there is an un-overlapping harmony in leading learners to the intended educational objectives of values education.

Islamic Boarding School Tradition

Islamic Boarding School tradition refers to peculiar and original values in the Islamic Boarding School domain that are maintained from one generation to another (in the Islamic Boarding School environment) since their establishment; the peculiar and original values of the Islamic boarding school are divided into two categories namely the traditional form and the contemporary form. On the other hand, the Modern Islamic Boarding School refers to Islamic boarding schools that adopted contemporary schooling forms but still maintain the Islamic boarding school tradition.

Location

The study is conducted in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School located in the Cigondewah Hilir Village, 7 km from the Capitol of West Java Province, Bandung. Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School occupies a 4-acre land and is equipped with the physical facilities with a student population of 970 santri (2010 data), consisting of 479 male santri and 491 female santri. They live in the four dormitory buildings and they study in 60 different classrooms. The santri is led by a Kyai and taught by 68 full-time teachers and 30 part-time teachers, consisting of 55 ustadz (male instructors) and 43 ustadzah (female instructors).

Results and Discussion

The Education Phenomena in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School

Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School is an Islamic boarding school that combines the salafiyah tradition and the modern madrasah educational system in its educational implementation. The salafiyah Islamic boarding schools emphasize the role of the Kyai in education and the use of classical Arabic Islamic holy

books in religious teachings. On the other hand, the madrasah system emphasizes a multilevel classical system and combines religious education and general science (read: secular) education in the structure of their curriculum. Both systems are organized in an integrated manner without institutional dualism; however, the educational process is conducted in dual-modes i.e. teaching and nurturing. The model is also referred to as Salafy-Madrafy Islamic Boarding School system. Therefore, Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School typologically is a modern Islamic boarding school with a centralistic leadership approach that is based on the charisma of the Kyai as the custodian of educative ideas. This aspect is apparent from the institutional structure with working units and Islamic boarding school activities that are very complex. Educative tasks and supporting tasks in the structure are segmented to sub-systems. With charismatic leadership, all of the policies are in the hands of the Kyai who served as the General Director of the Islamic Boarding School. The educative, administrative, institutional and financial policies are controlled by the Kyai and other educational agents, like the ustadz and supervisors, in spite of their status and their position are only executors of the Kyai's policies.

Such leadership is not part of the Islamic boarding school but exists as an individual initiative of the Kyai whose idea hinges the establishment of the Islamic boarding school. Therefore, the Islamic boarding schools often materialize from the potential ideas of the establishing Kyai. Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School with the praxis form is established by a Kyai with the following principles: (a) the ideality principle, the will to dedicate to the religion, so elements of worship with sincerity to perform good deeds are the basis of the movement; (b) the empirical-historical principle; the effectiveness of the Islamic boarding school education (salafiyah) to achieve the objectives of Islamic character education; (c) the pragmatic principle; considerations towards real interests in overcoming the demand of the century; and (d) the creativity-visionary principle; serving as an alternative for Islamic educational systems that suffered from quality degradation, ineffectiveness and inefficiency.

In the historical context of Islamic boarding school development, Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School is an educative phenomenon from the progressive dynamics of Islamic boarding school in encountering the demands of the century. In this case the Islamic boarding school displayed a high adaptation capacity toward the socio-political context and condition of the supra-system in which Islamic boarding schools existed. However, in maintaining the educative tradition, the Islamic boarding school turned itself into a "closed" open system but the system is not exclusive and did not alienate itself from the surrounding supra-culture. In this case, the Islamic boarding school attained an adaptational capacity through accommodation and the modification and adoption towards the external system that is stronger by maintaining fundamental traditional values. From the educative phenomenon in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School, it can be asserted that the Islamic boarding school is not a non-formal educational institution anymore because schooling is part of the Islamic boarding school. However, the school is institutionally still a communal institution that developed as the sub-culture from and to the community.

In adapting to the educational pragmatic demands, Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School adopted a formal system according to the Law on the national education system although the Islamic boarding school still maintains the tradition in efforts of developing Islamic characters. In the context of national education, Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School serves as a partner who sincerely helps in developing the community and the national characters. The Islamic boarding school had orientation towards aid provision because whether the school is granted aid or not, it should keep operating on its own capacity.

The Values Education Process in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School

In the process towards the values education phenomena in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School, the educational concept is returned to the essential meaning; the philosophical basic setting, the "normative-practical anthropology" (M.I. Soelaeman in Munawwar Rahmat, 2010:81-82). In the concept there are five educational aspects: (1) the educational teleological-normative aspect, namely the objective; (2) the anthropological aspects as the subjects that would be educated with values, namely the human beings with all of their dimensions; (3) the methodological aspect as an effort to internalize the values into the subject-participants; (4) the meditative-instrumentalist aspect as the internalization assisting tool and the values

actualization; and (5) the ideological aspect as the basis that became the motor for the values education action.

The Teleological-Normative Aspect of Values Education

Analysis of the educational objectives formulated in the vision, the mission and the objectives of Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School thalabul-ilmu shows that the thelos of education is full of values referred to as “value-based education.” The reason is essentially that the ultimate aim of the mission is to nurture learners to become people of good character. The ultimate objective is confirmed by the Kyai and other leaders in the Islamic boarding school. In their opinion, the educational objective is based on the Islamic teachings as delivered by Nabi Muhammad SAW namely: the first and the foremost thing educated to the human beings is the akhlakul karimah.

The akhlakul al-karimah is an Islamic concept of morality that includes reason, feeling, will and actions, and it is based on the awareness of doing good, which is a human disposition, manifestation given by Allah SWT since the creation of a human in the uterus. The spirit is the motor for the human beings to arrive at the deity goodness. In Islam, morality is a bound to values of goodness that are stipulated by the God. Therefore, morality in Islam refers to the pious or believing in God (Allah). Morality is a spirit that lives in the human beings’ internal aspect and morality is the spirit given by God to the human beings’ spirit. “Therefore, when I finish the physical creation and I give part of my spirit into My creation...” (Q.S. Al-Hijr:28-29). Therefore, spirit is the internal encouragement towards goodness and morality which is the work of the spirit that always leads to goodness.

Moreover, the concept of “humanity” as an educational objective in the concept Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School refers to individuals with akhlakul al-karimah who are supported by religion science and general science. To have akhlakul al-karimah would mean to display attitude, behavior and actions that are related to Islamic values that are derived from Al-Qur’an and the Sunnah of Nabi Muhammad SAW in which Nabi Muhammad SAW is the role model. From this perspective, it is apparent that the educational objective of the Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School is based on the religious foundation in which all of the educational levels should operate and should be operated under the search for the generosity of Allah so that the learning participants would find the meaning of their worship.

Anthropological Aspect as a Raw Input in Values Education

The values education system of Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School, the disposition aspect is the values-education-target within the educational process not only in the reasoning, the feeling and the action aspect but also in the innate desire and spiritual encouragement. Innate desire is considered as morality disturbance and destroyer while spirituality is considered as a motor and the strengthening part on of moral encouragement and for a weakened innate desire (syahwat). This is the reason why practically innate desire and spirituality weaken one another. If the spirituality becomes stronger, innate desire would be weaker (or even would not be active anymore); on the other hand, if the innate desire became stronger, spirituality would be weaker (or would even be covered).

So, the disposition (human beings’ potential dimensions) in relation to values education developed in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School includes the five dimensions of: logic, heart, spirit, desire and vital organs. All of these dimensions are placed in the values-education-target in order to develop (Islamic) character. The logic is developed by ta’lim (knowledge). The heart is developed by tilawah and tamrin moderated by Al-Qur’an readings and discipline (obedience of rules and regulations). The spirit is developed by tilawah and riyadhah (animated by worship: shalat sunnah, shaum, istighatsah, dzikir and the like). The desire is developed by tazkiyyah (strained and calmed with the elimination of negative tendencies known as takhalli in the definition of tasawuf). Last but not the least, vital organs are developed by amaliyah (good, positive and constructive activities).

The specification of each human beings' dimension in the context of the mission on the values education and the values learning is described in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1. The Five Human Beings Dimensions and the Learning

Dimensions	Characters	Aspects	Values Action	Learning
Spirit	Transcendence	Esoteric	Spiritualization	Animated
Reason	Rationality	Cognitive	Conceptualization	Understood
Feeling	Easy subjection	Affective	Internalization	Strengthened
Desire	Self-satisfaction	Psychomotoric	Dissonance	Controlled
Body	Ready to act	Motoric	Actualization	Bended

The Methodological Aspect as the Value Transfer Strategy

The educational methodology in relation to how to transform the learning participants' potentials became actual through efforts of influencing learners. The assumptions of educational methodology are that "humans are in a process of being," "humans can change," "human have will" and "human take decisions freely." According to Cumming (tt:178), in the praxis level values education encounters two options of values inculcation and the values clarification. Through the clarification approach values education serves merely to assist students in clarifying the values that they have. On the other hand, through the inculcation approach the values should be inculcated directly by means of teaching to students.

In the educational phenomena of Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School, the educational process has its own characteristics. Conceptually and theoretically, the values development system in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School is implemented through teaching, nurturing and the activities of the santri. Technically, the learning process is organized in three educative organization systems namely formal (teaching) system, non-formal (nurturing) system and informal system (creative activities in form of recreative, participative and dedicative activities). In the context of values education, the three systems are intended to develop aspects of values-knowing, values-feeling and values-acting.

Madrasah as a formal means for developing a cognitive aspect regarding goodness structurally and measurably directs learners on how to know. The Islamic boarding school as a leben umwelt (living environment), can be taken into account as an information educational environment so is the family learners learn about life values therefrom as learners develop the capacity of living together. Unconsciously, this environment replaces family functions such as the social function, recreation, the self-expression and the conservancy. The santri organization and the boy scout as a medium of expression and creativity as well as the medium of dedication are turned into a medium for developing the how-to-be and the how-to-do capacity.

The values education methods that is implemented in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School can be categorized into four approaches. The first is indoctrination (by means of classroom teaching, general lectures and motivating through incentives). The second is active-learning (by means of role modelling, participating habituation, practice and memorization tasks). The third is guidance and extension (by means of guidance, discipline publication, supervision, penalty, separation/segregation/isolation and sudden inspection). Last but not the least, the fourth category is conditioning (by means of discipline and educational atmosphere and situation structuring).

From the multiple methods implemented, the values learning process in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School tradition is overall oriented more to values-inculcation than values-clarification. At the same time, values inculcation is accompanied by efforts growing through multiple santri activities that enable actualization of values that have been inculcated for such a long time so they can develop rapidly.

Through the three learning systems and the four methodological approaches, the internalization and the externalization process (referring to the theory of Human System-Four Quadrant by Ken Wilber as having

been depicted in page 5 point 5) has a wide opportunity. The internalization process is a process in which values are “internalized” in students so that the values become students’ value and belief system. On the other hand, the externalization process is a process in which values that have become students’ value and system belief are externalized from the students’ self-experience in form of actions manifested in those values and belief system. The first process is mental activities (feeling) while the second process is the physical activities (acting). Within the values internalization process, “personality transformation” occurs, the changes in belief (and value commitment). Then, in the externalization process, “personality expression” occurs in form of actions, known as characters; in this case, the characters refer to the actual appearance of values personalized. Incultation and the self-clarification process in the five human dimensions are illustrated the following figure below.

Figure 1. The Process of Values Incultation and Values Growing Up

The strengthening efforts for the values internalization and externalization process in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School are pursued by: (1) performing civilization through consistent discipline; (2) eliminating dissonant factors; (3) pursuing continuity of values development process in space and time; and (4) evaluating personality during the learning process.

The Instrumental-Meditative Aspect in the Values Education Process

In transferring learning materials to learners, there should be media in addition to the methodological aspect that serves as the assisting tool to help learners internalize. Educational media that enables the “transfer” of educational content (knowledge, values, attitude, ideas, spirit and skills) to learners in a more effective way so that through this transfer learners become “new individuals” (“expected individuals”). In modern educational concepts and learning, educational media can include human, materials or events that establish a condition or that enable students attain knowledge, skills or attitude (Gerlach & Ely in Kustadi&Sucipto, 2011:7).

In Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School, overall, the educative potential possessed functioned as a values education media in which each of the medium would function in accordance with effective power that can be activated. The Kyai as the main teacher and ustadz as supporting teachers and executors of the Kyai’s

educative policies, in addition to serving as the source of information regarding values, serve as role models of Islamic values (disciplined, religious and educative); in other words, Kyai and ustadz serve as an exemplary medium. The learning materials, both of religion science and the general science i.e. the curriculum content and lessons, serve as conceptual medium. The physical facilities like buildings, classrooms, and the non-physical facilities, like the santri organization, the santri cooperative business unit, serve as the activation medium. On the other hand, the learning environment serves as a resonance medium that strengthens the values while time-space serves as the actual medium in which the santri have a wide opportunity to actualize the values they possess.

The Ideological Aspect as the Basis and the Spirit of the Values Education

The similarly important aspect, especially regarding values education in the character development, is the spirit that encourages the educational actors and learners in being involved in the educational process. The Islamic boarding school manifested through tradition in where the educational spirit is reduced to “low” idealism such as: title, position, huge payment and occupation. As a result, education is trapped in such “market constraints.”

In the context of character education, Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School turned the religion into a source of values, an internalization and externalization/actualization media, inspiration of the human concept of development, a motive of educative action, a source of manners of educating values and a reference in the development of educational ideas. The ideological religiosity in the values education of Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School is apparent in the vision, the mission, curriculum content and the implemented process and practice in overall educational implementation.

The educative spirit established by the Islamic religious teachings that worship served as a means for searching the generosity of Allah SWT, is the encouragement in the implementation of educative activities. In this Islamic boarding school, the Kyai, ustadz and santri are obliged to be in a single corridor of interest and of functional perception within the educational process to conduct religious imperatives. Therefore, the educational process contained devotion or worship values, holiness, generosity searching and the afterlife orientation and the educational process is implemented as an awareness toward life tasks (internal responsibility). So, teaching and learning are morale and serve as an imperative-theological matter.

In order to impact spiritual effects on values internalized, values education in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School is integrated into the religion subjects. As a result, the overall values are integrated into a religious spirit in which the moral values are considered a gift of God, therefore values are absolute and sacred. Ethical values are not part of the belief towards God because values are integrated into the Tauhid/Akhlak subject. Ethical values teaching is also intended to bring the learners closer to God; therefore, ethical values teaching is also integrated into the Akhlak/Tasawwuf subject. In addition, ethics and other life values are taught integrated in the Tafsir Al-Qur’an and Hadith subjects, as well as Tarikh Nabi and the ShabatShalih subjects.

In this Islamic boarding school, the concept of values and values education is framed in the deity awareness that performing good deeds is as ordered by God. The overall values are internalized and grown in the context of faith-based diversity; as a result, the educational process is religious-oriented. Therefore, values actualization in form of actions is encouraged by the imperative-theological awareness.

Findings

The findings of the study are related to three matters namely the characteristics of the values education process in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School, the integrative pattern of the values education and the construct of the integrative values education model that can be applied to educational institutions.

Characteristics of the Values Education Process in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School

From the results of analysis and interpretation of the values education phenomena in Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School, several principles can be formulated that form the characteristics of the values education process in the Islamic boarding school tradition:

- The intention to teach and to learn is mainly by prayer. The educational action is based on religious encouragement, which is eventually perceived as the order of God.
- Educational norms are directed to the development of personality with Islamic character; a personality that turns Islamic values (taqwa) to core values of faith, attitude and action. This personality has the nobility equipped with the both religious and general science.
- The learning subjects are merged into a complete personality concept that is established by fitriyah dimensions (spirit, reason, emotion, desire and body). Each of these dimensions has different capacity in the context of performing good deeds. Therefore, each dimension should be given different treatment in the values education process.
- The design of the values education system enables the occurrence of a comprehensive values learning process. A values education system by design features teaching, nurturing and activating and through the indoctrination, guidance, active-learning and conditioning approach.
- Values education content includes all types of necessary life values. The curriculum structure includes seven types of values (religions, ethics, social, work, hygiene, civics and esthetics) in which ethics are essential value and religion is the spirit of all values. Therefore, all decisions are referred to the religion (Islam).
- The methods (from the Islam teachings, the Islam traditions and others) are selected in order to enable the empowerment of all fitriyah dimensions in the values internalization and externalization process. The Islamic approach is preferred to be the basis of consideration both theoretically and empirically although the approach may be different from that of modern education.
- All of the potential educative resources that is possessed and that is available are benefitted as optimum (without mubadzir) and concomitant as possible as the values learning media for the learning subjects. These resources included the personal, material, scientific, physical, organizational and environmental aspect.
- The evaluation system is integrated into the assessment methods as a tool for changing the learning subjects' behaviors. As a tool for changing the learning subjects' behaviors, especially in relation to the aspect of moral and character, the personality assessment gained intensive attention that is provided during the learning process.

The characteristics of the values education phenomena in the modern Islamic boarding school tradition are totally in contradiction to the concept of secular Western values education. The contradiction can be found in the five essential aspects of education namely the teleological-normative aspect, the anthropological aspect, the methodological aspect, the meditative-instrumentalist aspect and the ideological aspect as well as in the guidance and extension concept and the educational axiology. The comparison on the aspects and the approaches can be viewed in the following Table.

Table 2. The Values Education Phenomena in the Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School in Comparison to the Modern Values Education Concept

Aspect	Modern/Western	Islamic Boarding School Tradition/Islam
Teleological	Freedom morality	Bound to the kindness values (<i>Akhlakul-karimah</i>)
Anthropological	Reason Emotion Action	Spirit Reason Feeling Desire Body Organ

Methodological	Clarification Confirmation	Inculcation Grow up (Self-Clarification)
Mediative- Instrumentalist	Religion-based values education model: (VCT, CMD, STS, MCM, and alike)	Exemplary medium Conceptual medium Activation medium Consonant medium
Ideological	Pragmatic Mundane Mundane necessity Faith separation	Religious <i>Ukhrawi (ta'abbudi)</i> Deity necessity Faith basis
GC	Guidance & Counselling Preventive Curative toward psychological disorder and deviation	Guidance and Extension Preventive by establishing resistance Curative by pursuing spiritual awareness
Educational Axiology	Humanistic- Pedagogics	Religious- Pedagogics

The Integrative Pattern of the Values Education Model in the Islamic Boarding School

The integration can be systemically integrated into the relationship among the four educational sub-systems as follows along with the status of each sub-system in the values education of the Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School.

- The integrality view toward the learning subjects stated that learning subjects served as the raw input in the process of Islamic teachings-based education namely the organism unity from the body, the desire, the reason, the sense, the feeling and the spirit; the five aspects then would be a unity as the values-education-target.
- The integrality on the manners of inculcating and of growing up values among the learning subjects through the various educational methods served as the strategy in the values education process that is in accordance with the human potential capacity. These methods had orientation toward the values inculcation and the values growing up. That enabled the values internalization and externalization/actualization process. All of these manners can also be pursued in order to strengthen resonant factors and to eliminate the dissonant factors toward the developed values internalization and externalization process. The overall methods are put into an interrelated unity which can be manifested to the educative actions that the learning subjects performed.
- The integral functionalization toward the educative potentials served as the medium of the values education process and the synergical and integral functionalization is conducted in order to achieve the objectives of personality and character development.
- Educational Agent as the Exemplary Medium
Kyai served as the value-figure for the Islamic boarding school values and the ustadz/ustadzah served as the Kyai assistants served as the medium for the santri in the process of self-identification. In other words, these figures served as the exemplary medium for the santri in capturing and developing their values.
- Learning Materials as the Conceptual Medium
The curriculum with all of the values-related lesson sets served instrumentally as a cognitive stimulant for the values internalization process.
- Physical and Non-Physical Facilities as the Activation Medium
The physical and the educative organizations served as the medium for the santri in actively activating and actualizing the values that is internalized.
- Educational Environments as the Resonance Medium

The Islamic boarding school complex and institution as an educational environment served as the place of creating conducive educational situations for the sake of strengthening the internalized values.

- Time and Space and the Actual Medium

Time and space as the gift of the nature served as an opportunity to perform the educative activities in the characters development optimally without any hesitation. Meanwhile in both aspects the santri performed their learning process continuously.

- The integrality of educational vision, mission, policy and action in the corridor of religion serves as the spirit, motor, of institutional structure that provided nuances in educative interaction. The spirit is Islamic values laid down in all pious actions as a form of worship. Therefore, as a form of worship all actions should be performed sincerely, in search of the God's generosity, with full of forgiveness or grace, under love toward humanity, goodness, usefulness and obedience towards religious norms. Therefore, the educational objectives in form of religious pedagogics are educational efforts based on religious values of each involved party

The pattern of the integrative relationship can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 2. The Pattern of Integrative Relationship in Values Education

The Integrative Values Education Model in the Tradition of the Modern Islamic Boarding School

The integral relationship in the values education system of Al-Basyariyah Islamic Boarding School can systemically be described in the following figure. The researcher referees to the values education model as the Azharian Integrative Values Education Model named after K.H. SaefulAzhar, the creator of the grand idea.

The philosophical foundation and basis of the integrative values education process implementation. Through the educational philosophical basis, practically the construct of the integrative values education model can be described in a flowchart consisting of educational objectives, educational programs, and the educational process as described in the figure above.

Conclusion

Al-Basyiriyah Islamic Boarding School in terms of educational-philosophy tends to be idealist-perennialist in the framework of Islamic teachings where the main objective and the core of the education is the development of nobility, al-akhlaq al-karimah, the ethical values are developed on akidah and the syarih of Islam. Therefore, in Al-Basyiriyah Islamic Boarding School the target of all subjects, both the religious and secular, is to form the akhlakul-karimah or the value-based education. Since character education is the essential mission of educational programs, Islamic boarding schools emphasize values development through strict discipline (regulation) implementation, habituation and role modelling of educators in addition to values development-related teachings. Therefore, Al-Basyiriyah Islamic Boarding School strictly controls implementation of daily discipline through routine and continuous supervision as well as strict enforcement by means of penalty provision. Discipline is a fundamental value that promotes ethics in Islamic boarding schools through performing the duties of implementing the educational vision and mission. The problems of discipline is very crucial for education as if education is identical to discipline; "Education without discipline is like snake without venom." Therefore, the values inculcation that goes along the spirit of Islam is given serious attention so almost all educational activities is full of the Islamic values. In order to achieve the condition, there should be an integral values education pattern that can be implemented simultaneously. Integration includes all educational segments in the institutional, structural-curriculum, methodological, learning system, program, scientific, development target, policy and leadership, possessed potential, santri activity, time and space, and learning participants' intention unity aspect both practically and conceptually.

In this context, Al-Basyiriyah Islamic Boarding School with local wisdom derived from the spirit of Islam implements the values education process with the values education system with the following characteristics: (1) values education is a single unity in the overall educational system; (2) values education is implemented integratively both by means of indoctrinative teaching and active-learning, by benefitting two educational paths, namely formal teaching and nurturing. so values education touches the knowing, feeling and acting aspect; (3) values education is directed towards all humanistic dimensions namely the body organs, the desires, the reason, the emotion and the spirit (jism, syahwat, 'aql, qalb and ruh) under multiple methods simultaneously; and (4) values education is implemented altogether with the aspect of faith so that it has strengthening power in its manifestation. Therefore, at praxis level, values education in Al-Basyiriyah Islamic Boarding School is in unison with religious education, both in terms of sources and in terms of materials, altogether with the spirit. In other words, values education, especially ethics education, is part of religion teaching both credentially and implemented as the part of ethics and morality development. Similarly, other values are developed in the context of religiosity, in that all life values are developed in accordance with the quality of religion improvement. Therefore, values education in the tradition of Islamic boarding schools is based on faithfulness that serves as the spirit of manifesting encouragement in actions.

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